

Use of *t*-Butyl Acetoacetate in the Preparation of Some Polynitrophenylacetones

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The use of *t*-butyl acetoacetate for the preparation of 6-(2'-benzofuryl)hexane-2,4-diones from β -2-benzofurylpropionic acids has been recently reported¹. The procedure involves condensation of the acids as their acid chlorides with *t*-butyl acetoacetate to furnish 3-*t*-butoxycarbonyl-6-(2'-benzofuryl)hexane-2,4-diones, which are easily transformed by *p*-toluenesulphonic acid in hot toluene to the crystalline 6-(2'-benzofuryl)hexane-2,4-diones, the reaction being followed by evolution of carbon dioxide.

The method has now been successfully extended to the preparation of polynitrophenylacetones (vide Table I) from 1-iodo-2,4-dinitro-(I), 2-chloro-1-iodo-4,6-dinitro-(II)², 2-bromo-1-iodo-4,6-dinitro-(III)², 1,2-di-iodo-4,6-dinitro-(IV)³, 4-chloro-1-iodo-2,6-dinitro-(V)², 1-iodo-2,6-dinitro-(VI)⁴, 1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-(VII) benzenes. The method offers the advantage over the old methods⁵ in that it provides superior products in better yields.

The polynitrophenylacetones crystallise in colorless needles except the one from picryl chloride, which is yellow. These react with the usual carbonyl reagents.

2,4-Dinitrophenylacetone.—To a solution of 1-iodo-2,4-dinitrobenzene (I) (5.8g., 0.02*M*) in ether (150 ml) was added the ethoxymagnesium derivative (equivalent to 0.6g. of magnesium) of *t*-butyl acetoacetate and the mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. The resulting complex was decomposed by dilute acetic acid. The ether layer after washing with sodium hydrogen carbonate solution and water and drying (Na_2SO_4) was evaporated. The residue was heated in toluene (150 ml) containing *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.5g.) on a boiling water bath until carbon dioxide was no longer evolved (about 4 hr.). When cooled, the solution was diluted with ether, washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide and then with water. The dried organic layer was concentrated finally under reduced pressure. The residue, when purified first by chromatography from benzene on silica and then by crystallisation from ethanol, furnished 2,4-dinitrophenylacetone in colorless needles (3.9g.), m.p. 78°. (lit.^{5a} m.p. 75°). (Found : N, 12.3. Calc. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$: N, 12.50%).

Its oxime crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 138° (lit.^{5a} m.p. 138°)

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2. Joshi and Deorha, *ibid.*, 1957, 2414.
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4. Parker and Read, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 3140.
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Following the above procedure, a few polynitrophenylacetones have been prepared and are described in Table I.

TABLE I

Halogenonitro- benzene used.	*Phenylacetone ^{6,7} formed.	%Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
II	R=Cl; R ₁ =R ₂ =NO ₂	70.0	100°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	Cl : 13.51	13.71
III	R=Br; R ₁ =R ₂ =NO ₂	67.3	115°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₅ N ₂ Br	Br : 26.28	26.37
IV	R=I; R ₁ =R ₂ =NO ₂	60.2	114°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₅ N ₂ I	I : 36.02	36.25
V	R ₁ =Cl; R ₂ =NO ₂	58.5	124°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	Cl : 13.42	13.71
VI	R ₁ =H; R ₂ =NO ₂	53.7	106°	C ₉ H ₈ O ₅ N ₂	N : 12.29	12.50
VII	R=R ₁ =R ₂ =NO ₂	69.6	92°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₇ N ₃	N : 15.33	15.61

Lit.^{5b} records m.p. 99°, 112°, 110°, 122°, 106°, and 89° respectively. The physical characteristics of their phenylhydrazones agreed with those given in the literature^{5c}.

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